

Study of oils from co-processing of coal and petroleum catalytic cracking slurry

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Abstract : A study was carried out on oils produced from co-processing of a coal and a petroleum catalytic cracking slurry (PCCS) in a 50-litre autoclave. Under the co-processing conditions used, the oil yield increases with an increase in co-processing temperature and time. It was also found that the co-processing under N₂ atmosphere yields significantly more oil than under H₂ atmosphere. The catalyst addition and catalyst type showed no significant effects on the oil yield. These results may be related to the properties of PCCS. The oil properties such as boiling point, sulfur distribution and chemical composition were investigated by FTIR and HPLC.

Keywords : Coal liquefaction, oil, co-process, catalyst, property.

Introduction

Co-processing of coal with petroleum residue by combining coal direct liquefaction technology with residue cracking technology has been considered to be the most economical coal liquefaction route at the present time. Petroleum catalytic cracking slurry (PCCS), with an annual production of more than 4 million tones in China, is difficult to be further processed because it has been catalyzed and cracked and contains some heavy metals¹. Some studies show that coal can adsorb some heavy metals in reaction process. On the other hand, China is a country of limited petroleum reserves and its main petroleum base is paraffinic, which is not suitable for manufacture of high grade paving asphalt^{2,3}. Co-processing of coal and PCCS was developed to produce high grade paving asphalt and paving asphalt modifier on mild conditions⁴⁻⁷. During this processing some oils were also produced, which can complement the fuel shortage, and types/properties of the oils vary from each other, and hence it should be concerned about oil yield/quality by researchers. Usually, oil yield and quality are related with processing conditions, so it is important for oil quality to investigate effect of co-processing conditions on the oil yield and properties.

In this paper, co-processing reaction between Yanzhou coal and PCCS, especially in oil yield and properties was studied.

Experimental

The co-processing was carried out in a 50-liter autoclave under hydrogen or nitrogen with or without a catalyst. The co-processing temperature ranged from 400 to 450 °C. The resident time and the pressure at the reaction temperature ranged 1–3 h and 8–14 MPa, respectively. The coal used was Yanzhou coal of China and the PCCS came from Shijiazhuang Petroleum Refinery. The ratios of the coal to the PCCS were 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. The properties of the coal and the PCCS are listed in Tables 1 and 2. A Fe or Mo catalyst was impregnated onto the coal particles at the catalyst loading of 1% for Fe and 0.04–0.4% for Mo. The 50-liter autoclave was directly connected to a 40-liter vacuum distillation unit. After the

Table 1. Proximate and ultimate analysis of Yanzhou coal

Proximate (%)			Ultimate (daf %)				
M _{ad}	A _{ad}	V _{daf}	C	H	O ^a	N	S
1.5	4.2	45.3	83.9	4.8	13.5	1.2	2.7

^aby difference.

Table 2. Group compositions of PCCS

Group compositions (%)			
Saturates	Aromatics	Resins	Asphaltene
6.7	65.7	18.7	8.9

reaction, the mixture was discharged into the distillation unit and the oil was distilled out at 310 °C and -0.090 MPa.

Oil yield can be calculated by the equation, which is as follows : Oil yield = oil weight/raw material organic weight × 100%.

The oil properties including boiling point distribution, sulfur distribution and chemical compositions were studied by GC, HPLC and FT-IR.

Results and discussion

The effect of reaction conditions on oil yield :

The oil yield under H₂ atmosphere significantly increased from 16.0 to 22.5% when the reaction time is increased from 1 to 3 h at 400 °C. The oil yield under H₂ increased from 16.0 to 19.6% when the reaction temperature is increased from 400 to 450 °C for reaction time of 1 h. The results comply with the fact that oil yield in H₂ increases with an increase in reaction temperature and the residence time. The ratio of coal to PCCS is another factor affecting the oil yield. The oil yield increased from 9.3 to 16.0% when the coal to PCCS ratio increased from 1 : 2 to 1 : 1 at 400 °C.

With increasing reaction temperature and reaction time, coal and PCCS crack to yield more free radicals. PCCS is not only a reactant but also a solvent that disperses coal particle and free radicals. Furthermore, a catalyst can transfer gaseous H₂ into active hydrogen and PCCS can transfer the active hydrogen to free radicals at reaction conditions to form stable compounds.

Table 3 shows oil yields under certain co-processing conditions. It is not expected to see the oil yield under N₂ atmosphere is much higher than that under H₂ atmosphere.

Table 3. The effect of different reaction conditions on oil yield at 400 °C for 1 h

Catalyst	No	Fe	Fe	Mo(0.4)	Mo(0.04)	Fe	Fe
Atmosphere	H ₂	N ₂	N ₂				
Coal : PCCS	1 : 1	1 : 1	1 : 2	1 : 1	1 : 1	1 : 1	1 : 2
Oil yield (%)	15.2	16.0	9.3	9.8	11.6	22.8	25.5

It is reasonable that the reaction condition is mild, main product is the heavy products for using as high grade paving asphalt modifier. Oil is by-product and oil yield is obviously lower than direct coal liquefaction or co-processing reaction. Under N₂ atmosphere poly-condensed is obviously main reaction, but coal pyrolysis can lead to oil product, even poly-condensed can further produced oil, such as H₂ emission in coal coking. So the reaction result that N₂ atmosphere yielded more oil is only under the special conditions. In addition, the result shows that the catalysts have only a little effect on the oil yield. These results, however, do not necessarily indicate that catalysts are not needed by the co-processing and that N₂ should be used in the co-processing, instead, the results may suggest that the effect of catalyst and atmosphere on the co-processing is mainly on the quality of the products, as shown by significant pressure variation during the co-processing when different catalysts and different atmosphere were used.

Compared to the Fe catalyst, the Mo catalyst resulted in the largest pressure decrease during the co-processing at 400 °C, indicating the largest consumption of H₂, which is consistent with the general understanding that Mo is a better catalyst than Fe for hydrogenation of coal. Compared to the Mo catalyst, the Fe catalyst not only resulted in small pressure decrease in the co-processing but also showed a narrower temperature range at which the pressure decrease occurred. Compared to the treatments with the catalyst, the pressure decrease in the co-processing without a catalyst is very small, indicating limited H₂ consumption. When N₂ atmosphere was used, however, the co-processing pressure always increased with increasing co-processing time, indicating that light products were formed, which corresponds to an increase in oil yield in Table 3.

Boiling point distribution of oils :

Boiling point distribution directly reflects oil compositions. Fig. 1 shows the boiling point distribution of oils obtained at co-processing temperatures of 400, 425 and 450 °C when Fe catalyst was used. The co-processing conditions were H₂ pressure of 5.0 MPa (cold) and 1 h.

The results show that the oils can be categorized into two fractions, with boiling points of lower than 270 °C (light-fraction) and greater than 270 °C (heavy-fraction).

Fig. 1. Boiling point distributions of the oils obtained at different co-processing temperatures.

The higher co-processing temperature results in the more light-fraction and the less heavy-fraction, and the lower co-processing temperature produces the less light-fraction and the more heavy-fraction, which suggests the more extensive cracking at high temperatures. The feed coal to PCCS ratio also affects the boiling point distribution of the oils. The oil obtained at the coal to PCCS ratio of 1 : 2 has the more light-fraction and the less heavy-fraction than that obtained at a coal to PCCS ratio of 1 : 1. This suggests that the light-fraction may be mainly generated from the PCCS instead of the coal because that the PCCS used is a product of high temperature processing which should be thermally more stable than the coal used. The effects of N_2 and H_2 atmospheres on the boiling point distribution of the oils are shown in Fig. 2 for co-processing temperature of 400 °C. The oil can also be categorized into two fractions as did in Fig. 1. The N_2 atmosphere yields less amount of light-fraction and more amount of heavy-fraction than the H_2 atmosphere does, suggesting more extent of condensation reactions under N_2 at-

Fig. 2. Boiling point distributions on different atmosphere.

mosphere. As we known, H_2 atmosphere is preferred in refinery due to saturation of double bond, possibility of hydro cracking and also gives cleaner fuel of low boiling components. The low boiling components have high market values and good utilization properties. From this, the paper does not indicate that N_2 should be used in the co-processing. In general, nitrogen atmosphere is never recommended in industrial practice. It is interesting to point out that under the same co-processing conditions the Fe catalyst and the Mo catalyst yield oils with similar boiling point distribution. This, along with the results in Table 3, suggests that the effect of PCCS on the co-processing is more profound than the catalyst due to the highly aromatic nature of the PCCS, which has high solubility for free radicals and hydrogen, and high capability for hydrogen shuttling. This suggestion is further supported by the fact that the boiling point distribution of oils from catalytic co-processing is similar to that from non-catalytic co-processing.

Sulfur distribution :

A FPD detector for sulfur was used in parallel to a FID detector during the measurement of boiling point distribution on a GC. At a coal to PCCS ratio of 1 : 2, the sulfur in the oil is associated mainly with the fractions with boiling points of 300– 400 °C. This sulfur distribution pattern change insignificantly with changes of co-processing temperature and coal to PCCS ratio. In addition, oil sulfur distribution was also analyzed in H_2 and N_2 atmosphere condition and the result is similar to that sulfur distribution rule with changes of co-processing temperature and coal to PCCS ratio, namely the sulfur distribution pattern also change insignificantly with changes of atmosphere. As we known, another important effect factor is oil yield to sulfur distribution. It suggests that sulfur migration is sophisticated in the co-processing process, so we can't relate sulfur distribution with changes of atmosphere. These results suggests that the range of co-processing conditions used in this work is relatively narrow which can not cause significant change in cracking of coal structure and hydro-treating of coal derived oils.

Chemical composition :

Group composition of the oils is analyzed by a HPLC coupled with both ultraviolet and differential refractometer detectors. The results in Table 4 show that the oil is mainly composed of aliphatic, two-ring and three-ring aromatic compounds and polar compounds, and asphaltenes. About 50% contents are two-ring and three-ring aromatic

compounds. The content of four-ring aromatic compounds is small in oil, less than 5%. Polar compounds are about 5–10%. Asphaltenes vary from 7 to 20%. These data may suggest again that the catalysts and atmosphere have

Table 4. Group compositions of oils obtained at 400 °C for 1 h

Catalyst	–	Fe	Fe	Mo(0.4)	Fe
Atmosphere	H ₂	H ₂	H ₂	H ₂	N ₂
Coal : PCCS	1 : 1	1 : 1	1 : 2	1 : 1	1 : 1
Aliphatic	21.86	26.14	15.72	8.50	19.22
One-ring	9.91	6.69	5.59	10.71	8.31
Two-ring	28.95	21.65	27.84	35.39	21.91
Three-ring	21.53	25.90	23.49	23.99	20.69
Four-ring	3.47	1.75	2.98	1.26	2.58
Polar	6.33	9.24	7.77	6.95	7.39
Asphaltene	7.95	8.63	16.60	13.20	19.89

only limited effects on the oil quality and that the PCCS probably is the main factor that affects the co-processing results. It should be pointed out that co-processing oil can be used as fuels for making up shortage of petroleum, but it must be blended in the refinery to proper market them, mainly basing the fractions and chemical composition of the oil. In addition, about 50% contents are two-ring and three-ring aromatic compounds, which is useful for chemical products refined further.

FT-IR analyses :

A FT-IR spectrometer was used to analyze the oil obtained under various conditions. The results show that the co-processing conditions have no significant effect on oil quality, as shown in Fig. 3 for oils obtained using Mo and Fe catalysts.

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectrum of oil.

Conclusion

(i) The oil yield increases with an increase in co-processing temperature and time under the co-processing conditions used.

(ii) The co-processing under N₂ atmosphere yields significantly more oil than under H₂ atmosphere.

(iii) The catalyst addition and catalyst type showed no significant effects on the oil yield.

(iv) The N₂ atmosphere yields less amount of light-fraction and more amount of heavy-fraction than the H₂ atmosphere does, it can be contributed to high asphaltene contents by HPLC.

(v) S distribution and oil chemical structure are not obviously related with reaction conditions.

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